

EFFECT OF COLOUR

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Colours can stimulate and excite people, increase their appetite, make them feel warm or make them feel tranquil. Red simply makes you excited according to those who study chromo dynamics. Coke's website is red – it gives you a feel of a lazy, hot summer day – just when you feel the need to drink Coke. There's more to colours in web design than just the emotional factor. People tend to gamble more under red light conditions than under blue light. Colours have impact on performance. Red lights make people act quicker and feel more powerful, which is not always beneficial, while blue makes people think more before acting. There is a reason STOP signs are red – you need to act right away and stop the vehicle you drive, otherwise you are in danger.

Understand the psychological meanings of your choices for website colours

- **Red** is attention-getting
- **Orange** is adventurous and affordable
- **Yellow** is cheerful and fun
- **Green** is balancing and reflects nature
- **Turquoise** is clarity of thought and communication
- **Blue** is honesty and trustworthiness
- **Indigo** in integrity and sincerity
- **Purple** is individual, creative and inventive
- **Magenta** is compassionate, spiritual yet practical
- **Pink** is loving, compassionate, understanding, youthful and romantic
- **White** is simplicity, cleanliness, order and the new slate to write upon
- **Black** is authority, power and control
- **Gray** is neutral, refined and contemporary
- **Brown** is comfort, dependability and friendliness
- **Silver** will appear as gray on a website so read the information on gray to endure that is the message you wish to send
- **Gold** can appear as a dirty yellow which is not positive for any business. Adjust gold on your website to a golden yellow and read the meaning of the colour yellow to see if it imparts the message you want to send

USE OF COLOUR

It need to understand where we can use these colour tips. We can use of colour in website design. Specifically, talking about the colour scheme of a website, which includes the tint of hero graphics, headline type, borders, backgrounds, buttons, and popup.

In the example below, Ninja.Jump uses a green-yellow-red colour scheme in their logo, phone number, video, menu bar, graphics, category menu, sub headings, and sidebar. Colour is a tricky thing. We have to use it in the right way, at the right time, with the right audience, and for the right purpose. For example, if you are selling bouncy jump houses — those things that kids play in. we should not use a black website. For the jump house site, we want lots of bright and vibrant colours, probably some reds, greens, and maybe a splash of yellow for good measure. If, on the other hand, we are selling a product to women, we don't want to use brown or orange. Maybe that's why L'oreal uses black and white, with purple overlay, in their e-commerce homepage. It's all depends on using the right colour psychology.

1. Women don't like gray, orange, and brown. They like blue, purple, and green. The sociological differences between colour preferences is a whole branch of study unto itself. We can mention the colours preferred, and disliked, by the two genders. In a survey on colour and gender, 35% of women said blue was their favourite colour, followed by purple (23%) and green (14%). 33% of women confessed that orange was their least favourite colour, followed by brown (33%) and gray (17%). Other studies have corroborated these findings, revealing a female aversion to earthy tones, and a preference for primary colours with tints. Look at how this is played out. Visit nearly any e-commerce site whose target audience is female, and we'll find these female colour preferences affirmed.

Milani Cosmetics has a primarily female customer base. Thus, there's not a shred of orange, gray, or brown on the homepage. Woman's Day uses all three of the favourite colours of women (blue, purple, and green) on their homepage, thus inviting in their target audience. Most people think that the universally-loved female colour is pink. It's not. Just a small percentage of women choose pink as their favourite colour. Thus, while pink may suggest femininity in colour psychology, this doesn't mean that pink is appealing to all women, or even most women. Use colours other than pink — like blue, purple, and green — and we may improve the appeal of our e-commerce website to female visitors and that may, in turn, improve conversions.

2. Men don't like purple, orange, and brown. Men like blue, green, and black.

If we are marketing to men, these are the colours to stay away from: purple, orange, and brown. Instead, use blue, green, and black. These colours — blue, green, and black — are traditionally associated with maleness. However, it comes as a slight surprise to some that brown isn't a favourite pick.

3. **Use blue in order to cultivate user's trust.** Blue is one of the most-used colours, with good reason. A lot of people like blue. Blue colour delivered some messages:

The colour blue is a colour of trust, peace, order, and loyalty.

Blue calls to mind feelings of calmness and serenity. It often is described as peaceful, tranquil, secure, and orderly.

There is wide agreement in the research community on the psychological effects of the colour blue. Its subtle message of trustworthiness and serenity is true. We can use this to our advantage on our

website and landing pages. The world's biggest social network is blue. For a company whose core values are transparency and trust, this probably is not an accident. A company that serves as a conduit for billions of rupees, HDFC, also prefers the colour blue. Chances are, this helps to improve their trustworthiness. If they were to try, say, red or orange as the theme colour and branding, they probably wouldn't have the same level of conversion like Bank of Baroda.

Blue is, in fact, a colour heavily used by many banks. Like here's HDFC bank. Although blue is pretty much an all-round great colour, it should never be used for anything related to food. Dieters have used blue plates to successfully prevent them from eating more. Evolutionary theory suggests that blue is a colour associated with poison. There aren't very many blue foods — blueberries and plums just about cover it. Thus, never use blue if you're selling foodie stuff.

4. Yellow is for warnings. Yellow is a colour of warning. Hence, the colour yellow is used for warning signs, traffic signals, and wet floor signs. It seems odd, then, that some colour psychologists declare yellow to be the colour of happiness. Business Insider reports that “brands use yellow to show that they're fun and friendly.” There is a chance that yellow can suggest playfulness. However, since yellow stimulates the brain's excitement centre, the playfulness feeling may be simply a state of heightened emotion and response, not exactly sheer joy.

Colour psychology is closely tied to memories and experiences. So, if someone had a very pleasant experience with someone wearing a yellow shirt, eating at a fast food establishment with yellow arches, or living in a home with yellow walls, then the yellow colour may cause joy by memory association. One of the most-cited “facts” about the colour yellow is that it makes babies cry and people angry. To date, I have not found any study that backs up this claim, even though everyone is fairly comfortable repeating it.

If you find the study about cranky babies and angry people living in yellow-walled houses, please let me know. I'm pretty sure that babies are going to cry and people are going to get ticked, regardless of the paint colour. Whatever the case, it does seem true that “yellow activates the anxiety centre of the brain,” as reported by one colour expert. A heightened anxiety level during any website experience is never a good thing, unless it comes in small doses. Thus, a yellow call to action may create just a touch of anxiety that's needed to make them click the desired call to action. Use yellow in small doses unless you want to cause unnecessary anxiety.

5. Green is ideal for environmental and outdoor products. Perhaps the most intuitive colour connection is green — the colour of outdoors, eco-friendly, nature, and the environment. Green essentially is a chromatic symbol for nature itself. Apart from its fairly obvious outdoorsy suggestiveness, green also is a colour that can improve creativity. Labelled “the green effect,” one study indicated that participants had more bursts of creativity when presented with a flash of green colour as opposed to any other colour. If the focus of website has anything to do with nature, environment, organic, or outdoors, green should be your colour of choice.

Green isn't just about nature, though. Green also is a good call to action colour, which states that we remember things better if they stand out. You remember the Statue of Liberty because it's big, tall, and green. In colour psychology, the isolation effect occurs when a focus item, such as a conversion step, is the only item of a particular colour. The technique works wonders for calls to action, and green is an ideal choice.

All of Dell's conversion elements are green.

The word "green" itself is a buzzword for environmental awareness and appreciation. Using the word and the colour itself can lend an environmental aura to our website, improving our reputation among those who are passionate about environmental concerns.

6. Orange is a fun colour that can create a sense of haste or impulse. The positive side of orange is that it can be used as the "fun" colour. Orange helps to "stimulate physical activity, competition, and confidence." This may be why orange is used heavily by sports teams and children's products. In fact, there are a ton of sports teams that use orange: Florida Gators, Clemson Tigers, Boise State Broncos, Syracuse, New York Knicks, New York Mets, San Diego Chargers, etc. Amazon.com uses orange in their "limited time offer" banner. The colour suggests urgency, which makes the message more noticeable and actionable. It makes sense. Orange means active. Orange means fun. Orange means togetherness. Because it's a loud and warm colour. However, orange can be slightly overwhelming. Orange will be used sparingly to bring your attention to something, but not so much as to overwhelm the actual message of the advert.

7. Black adds a sense of luxury and value.

The darker the tone, the more luxury it is, says our internal colour psychology. Black describes as "elegance, sophistication, power," which is exactly what luxury designers and high-end e-commerce sites want you to feel. The article goes on to describe black as the colour of "timeless, classic" which helps further explain the use of black in high-value products.

In a Business Insider piece on colour and branding, Black can also be seen as a luxurious colour. Black, when used correctly can communicate glamour, sophistication, exclusivity. Louis Vuitton handbags are not cheap. Absent from the site are colours and designs of whimsy and fun. This is serious value. Lamborghini does the same thing. Black is the name of the game. If you are selling high-value luxury consumer items on your website, black probably would be a good choice.

8. Don't neglect white. In most of the colour psychology material I read, there is a forgotten feature. Maybe that's because colour theorists can't agree on whether white is a color or not. I don't really care whether it is or not. What I do know is that copious use of white space is a powerful design feature. Take, for example, the most popular website in the world. It's basically all white:

White is often forgotten, because its primary use is as a background colour. Most well-designed websites today use plenty of white space in order to create a sense of freedom, spaciousness, and breathability.

CONCLUSION

The Internet is a colourful place, and there is a lot that can be accomplished by using colour in the right way, at the right time, with the right audience, and for the right purpose.

You may not be in a position to rewrite your style guide and pick your own website colour palette or font colours on the email template. So, how can you use colour psychology in these situations? There are a few options:

- Use psychology-appropriate colours that match the existing colour scheme. Sure, you need to adapt to the colour scheme, but you can still use a splash of strategic colour here and there.
- The more freedom you have in your colour scheme, the better. Here are some solid takeaways as you implement colour psychology into your website:
- **Test several colours.** Despite what some may say, there is no *right* colour for a conversion text or button. Try a green, purple, or yellow button. Explore the advantages of a black background scheme vs. a white background. Find out which works best for your audience and with your product.
- **Don't just leave colour choice up to your designer.** Colour is a conversion issue, not just an "Oh, it looks good" issue. Colour aesthetics is not everything. Colour conversion effects are important! You should be heavily involved in the colour selection of your landing pages in order to improve your conversions.
- **Avoid colour overload.** Don't go overboard. White is a colour, and it should be your BFF colour, too. Reign in your colour enthusiasm with a whole lot of white. Too many colours can create a sense of confusion.